

A Performance Appraisal of the Pedagogic in-Service Training Programme (ISTP) Multipliers in C.B.C. Secondary Schools of the North-West Region: Teachers' Perspective

Vanity Mugob Nshukwi

BSc GEO, PGDE (Hons), MEd (Hons), PhD in View, University of Buea, Buea, Cameroon

ABSTRACT

This paper sought to investigate the level of utilization of the prerequisites to supervision of instruction by the ISTP Multipliers in CBC secondary schools of the NWR: teachers' perspective. The study progressed as guided by a specific research question: To what extent do the ISTP Multipliers use interpersonal skills in supervision of instruction? This research question was transformed into a research hypothesis. The case study research design was used with proportionate and random sampling techniques respectively to ensure that respondents from all the schools were represented equally. Questionnaire for teachers was the instrument used for data collection. Data were analysed using statistical packages for social sciences (SPSS) version 21.0 for windows. Results were reported using descriptive statistics. Chi-square and student t-tests were used to determine relationships between respondents' demographic characteristics and their view on some attributes of the ISTP Multipliers. The decision rule was to reject the null hypothesis where the computed mean was statistically significantly greater than the expected value and accept the alternative hypothesis. Following this rule all the alternative hypotheses were rejected and the null hypotheses accepted. Recommendations were made to the Education secretary of the CBC, the ISTP Coordinator, the Principals and teachers of the schools concerned, the ISTP Multipliers in order to improve performance levels of the ISTP Multipliers. Suggestions for further research were given.

KEYWORDS: Performance Appraisal, Pedagogic In-service Training Program, Multipliers, C.B.C Secondary Schools, North West Region, Teachers' Perspective

INTRODUCTION:

According to Law No. 98/004 of 14th April 1998 to lay down guidelines for education in Cameroon, chapter I Section 2 part 1 states that education shall be a top priority of the nation and that it shall be provided by the state and private sector partners shall assist. This implies that the lay private and faith-based schools in Cameroon are partners assisting the state in the education of Cameroonian citizens. The CBC is one of the private sector partners in the provision of education at the basic and secondary levels. Moreover, chapter III section 37 part 2 of the above mentioned Law states that the teacher shall be the principal guarantor of quality education. This implies that in talking about quality education the teacher features at the centre because if he/she is apt in capability, achievement and efficiency, quality education is likely to be guaranteed.

The CBC Education Department uses ISTP Multipliers to provide continuing professional development support to teachers and the policy was adopted in the 1997/98 academic year and has since then functioned in phases. Two main evaluations of the programme have been carried out since inception. The first evaluation was done in 2004 and the second in 2010 by the first set of ISTP pedagogic Advisers and by a team from the University of Edangen-Nuremberg

How to cite this paper: Vanity Mugob Nshukwi "A Performance Appraisal of the Pedagogic in-Service Training Programme (ISTP) Multipliers in C.B.C. Secondary Schools of the North-West Region: Teachers' Perspective" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-6, October 2019, pp.914-928, URL: <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd29265.pdf>

IJTSRD29265

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

Germany respectively. These evaluations were carried out from the perspectives of the managers of the programme and the external sponsors from Germany. However, the cardinal aim of this paper is to do a performance appraisal of the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers from the perspective of CBC secondary school teachers in the NWR; precisely evaluating the extent to which the prerequisites to supervision of instruction are being used by the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers. An evaluation from the perspective of the teachers „completes“ the feedback component of the system as it reflects the teachers' perception of the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers' work. This is worthwhile because it gives the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers a true picture of the work they are doing, how much they comply to and how far they deviate from acceptable standards. This is supposed to be the "feedback" component in what is intended to be a helping relationship between the Multipliers and the teachers. It is in this vein that Killer (1998) opines that teacher performance evaluation is to determine competence, assess strengths, provide support and mentoring and assure continued growth through differential experiences. Furthermore, to Glickman (1990) and Sergiovanni (1987), a cordial relationship should exist between the supervisor (pedagogic ISTP Multiplier in this case) and the teachers

because the intention of supervision is to provide teachers with the needed support in instruction.

The aims of the above-mentioned evaluations were as follows:

- To measure the activities and achievements of the ISTP under the captions; school visits and workshops, seminars for teachers, HIV/ AIDS education, the trainee programme and promotion of student-centred and independent learning (Report on Evaluation of ISTP, April, 2004) and
- To find out what effects the ISTP had on students' academic achievements and what effects it had on teachers' didactical competences and professional beliefs, in that order.

According to the reports emanating from the reviews the impact of ISTP and the extent to which it was affecting students' academic achievements was positive. This was as revealed by the test scores of students from ISTP and Non-ISTP schools, shown on table 1.

Table 1: Test scores of students from ISTP and Non-ISTP schools (as of 2004).

School	Achieved Points	SD
ISTP -1	466	83
ISTP-2	496	83
ISTP-3	496	104
ISTP-4	449	89
ISTP-5	480	139
ISTP-6	500	86
Non- ISTP-1	418	101
Non- ISTP-2	450	84
Non- ISTP-3	453	85
Non- ISTP-4	426	124
Non- ISTP-5	541	94
Average	470.45	100

Source: Report on the Evaluation of the ISTP, July, 2004, p13.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Since inception of the programme no performance appraisal has been carried out from the perspective of teachers. This implies that there is no clear picture of the quality of work the Multipliers have been doing so far from the standpoint of those with whom they interact in the field (the teachers). This necessitates a study of this nature because it gives a clear picture of the job being done by the internal supervisors since they (the teachers) are the immediate consumers of the services of the supervisors. Given the implicit meaning of the term „prerequisite“ it is seen that the supervisory process cannot be effective if the supervisors do not have a proficient mastery of these prerequisites. If the Education Department of the CBC sets resources aside for this supervisory team without empirical evidence of how satisfactorily they are performing their duty, then there is a problem. This is because such investment will be done just for the sake of it and not necessarily in a bid to adequately address the needs that face these supervisors. As such the resources set aside for this may be infinitesimal or in excess. Either of the cases indicates an improper approach to harness available resources to achieve organisational goals. Therefore, knowledge of what the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers are doing in the field will help the authorities of the CBC Education Department to make necessary

adjustments both in allocation of budgets and administration of the supervisors (especially with respect to accountability). Such knowledge also serves as a guide to the Multipliers and the CBC Education Department authorities to rectify any highlighted shortcomings.

The above points show clearly that it is not healthy for such a programme as this to have been operating for as long as fourteen years without considering any official feedback from the „direct consumers“ of the Multipliers' services.

Drawing from Blasé and Blasé's (2004) submission on feedback, we see that feedback helps Multipliers in the same dimension as it does for the teachers, bringing them face to face with their actual output and what they can do to perform better. They wrote “feedback should not be a formality, but should serve as a guide for instructional improvement when it is given genuinely; feedback reflectively informs teacherbehaviour and this results in teachers implementing new ideas, trying out a variety of instructional practices, responding to student diversity, and planning more carefully and achieving better focus” (Blasé and Blasé, 2004).

Since supervision is very important to the health of the teaching-learning process, how teachers perceive their immediate supervisors (the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers) becomes a worthwhile area for research. This study set out to appraise from teachers' standpoint, the extent to which the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers are applying the prerequisites to supervision of instruction as a means to performing their tasks of supervision of instruction.

Objective

To find out whether the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers in the said schools use interpersonal skills in the supervisory process at acceptable levels and whether

Research Question

- How far do the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers use interpersonal skills in supervision of instruction?

Research Hypothesis

The pedagogic ISTP Multipliers in CBC secondary schools of the NWR do not use interpersonal skills in supervision of instruction at acceptable levels.

BACKGROUND

Supervision of instruction emerged as a field of study at the onset of the twenty-first century due to the increased level of bureaucracy in schools and public demand for the control over the school curriculum (Karier, 1982; Bolin, 1987), cited in Chuo (2007).

In colonial New England supervision of instruction began as a process of external inspection; one or more local citizens were appointed to inspect both what the teachers were teaching and what the students were learning. The inspection theme was to remain firmly embedded in the practice of supervision.

The history of supervision as a formal activity exercised by educational administrators within a system of schools did not begin until the formation of the common school in the late 1830s. During the first half of the nineteenth century,

superintendents initially inspected schools to see that teachers were following the prescribed curriculum and that students were able to recite their lessons. The multiplication of schools soon made it an impossible task for superintendents and the job was delegated to the school principal. In the early decades of the twentieth century, the movement towards scientific management in both industrial and public administration had an influence on schools and at much the same time, child centred and experience-based curriculum theories of European educationists such as Friedrich Froebel, Johann Pestalozzi and Johann Herbert as well as the prominent American philosopher John Dewey, were also affecting schools. These school supervisors often found themselves caught between the demand to evaluate teachers scientifically and the simultaneous need to transform teaching from a mechanistic repetition of teaching protocols to a diverse repertory of instructional responses to students' natural curiosity and diverse levels of readiness. This tension between supervision as a uniform, scientific approach to teaching and supervision as a flexible process between teacher and supervisor involving the shared professional discretion of both was to continue throughout the century.

In the second half of the century, the field of supervision became closely identified with various forms of clinical supervision. It was initially developed by Harvard professors Morris, Cogan and Anderson and their graduate students, many of whom subsequently became professors of supervision in other universities, blended elements of "objective" and "scientific" classroom observation with aspects of collegial coaching, rational planning and flexibility inquiry-based learning. In 1969, Robert Goldhammer proposed the following five stage process in clinical supervision: a pre-observation conference between supervisor and teacher concerning elements of the lesson to be observed, classroom observation, a supervisor's analysis of notes from the observation and planning for the post-observation conference, a post-observation conference between the supervisor and the teacher and a supervisor's analysis of the post-observation conference.

THE ISTP PROGRAMME

The ISTP is an educational programme of two protestant churches in Cameroon namely, the CBC and the PCC. In the 1993/94 academic year, the CBC and PCC adopted this Programme (ISTP) for teachers which went operational in 1997. More than 36 secondary and 200 primary schools are involved in the activities of the programme. The programme has trained about three hundred and fifty (350) secondary school teachers and one thousand two hundred and fifty (1250) primary school teachers of the CBC and PCC since the 1997/98 academic year.

The ISTP conducts on-the-job training of teachers in learner-centred, participatory and active pedagogy. It also works directly with students and pupils. According to the ISTP journals of 24th April, 2010, 19th December, 2013 and 1st September, 2014 the vision of ISTP centres on "Justice, Education for Liberation and Education for Life" in the process of school quality improvement. The mainstream activities of the ISTP include gender, democracy and good governance, environmental Education, HIV/AIDS and life skills. The ISTP has since inception trained over sixty (60) trainers called "Multipliers" who carry out on-the-job

professional development of teachers in specific locations. The ISTP is therefore a support institution for several schools of the aforementioned denominations (Njobati, 2013).

The goal of this program is to enhance learner-centred and activity based teaching/learning strategies thereby improving the quality of education in the CBC and PCC schools. The development of competences through the cognitive activation of learners, use of group work and a variety of various forms of cooperative and collaborative learning, promotion of positive values, and development/use of learner-centred schemes of work, production and use of teaching aids from cheap or readily available resources such as local/ salvaged material, characterise the ISTP. Since inception the programme has been operating in phases and is currently in phase five. These phases have operated as outlined in the paragraphs below. An outline of the terms of reference for the programme Multipliers according to the ISTP journal of 24th April, 2010 are to:

1. Provide in-service training to teachers through planned and intentional interactions with them during seminars / workshops, group activities and one-on-one discussions, in a bid to link theory to practice.
2. Be intentional about promoting awareness of the new pedagogic approach among teachers.
3. Produce and use relevant didactic material (especially from local and salvaged material) and help the teachers do same.
4. Ensure a culture of lesson planning and lesson observation, observing the ethical stages of pre- and post- observation meetings.
5. Inculcate and promote democratic principles and good values in students by helping them to democratically select their prefects during school elections.
6. Use a mastery of the necessary methods and skills together with a blend of learner-centred approaches to lesson delivery and supervision in order to ensure cordiality and tact in the discharge of their duties.

It should be noted that the various phases of the programme have terms of reference and these terms of reference are derivatives of the general objectives stated above. This is to say that a careful examination of what the Multipliers are expected to do during any of the phases would reveal a vivid correlation with one or more aspects of the general objectives stated above.

The programme was adopted in 1993 and the following outline presents details that led to its onset in the CBC and PCC schools. In September and November 1993, the request for an in-service training programme was made to the German Development Service (DED) by the authorities of the CBC and the PCC and in February 1994 a survey was carried out by the DED experts in the education departments of these two protestant churches in response to their request. According to these experts feasibility of the programme was ascertained and so, the request was approved. In May 1996, an application was forwarded for the funding of the first phase of the programme to the Protestant Association for Cooperation in Development (EZE) in Germany by the Moderator of the PCC. In November 1996, a Cooperation and Audit Agreement was signed between this Cooperation and the education departments of the two protestant churches with the moderator of the PCC as main signatory. The phases of the programme, their dates and durations are as shown on table 2.

Table 2: Phases of the ISTP and their durations

Phase of programme	Date	Duration
Phase I	January, 1997-December, 2000	3 years, 11 months
Phase II	January, 2001-April, 2005	4 years, 3 months
Phase III	July 2005-August 2009	4 years 1 month
Phase IV	September 2009-August 2013	4 years, 11 months
Phase V	September 2013-present	1 year, 1 month (is still ongoing)

Source: Compiled from official documents from the ISTP Head Office.

In January 1997 the first phase of the programme began with EZE providing the funding for the running cost and equipment while the DED provided the personnel. Phase one went operational in January 1997 and it progressed with the following specific objectives; to make the teaching of science subjects relevant, related to life and less abstract, to address gender issues, environmental education and main stream aspects, to train counterparts within a period of two years obtaining batch one in 1998 and batch two in the year 2000. Management during this phase (phase one) was in the hands of the DED. In March/April 1998, the programme was evaluated with the outcome being generally positive and the main recommendation being an extension to the arts subjects. In the year 2000 the programme had her pioneer set of Cameroonian pedagogic advisers being Messrs Akuo Gideon, Anye Richard (of blessed memory), and Njobati Frederick.

Phase two began in January 2001 and ended in April 2005 with the aim of; intensifying training in the teaching of science subjects, extending special approaches to the teaching of arts subjects, training of batch three trainees in September 2001 and batch four in September 2005.

Phase three started in July 2005 with the following aims; to put in place a management structure following the management procedures, to implement project exigencies, to effect the handing over procedure and the gradual taking over by the protestant churches concerned (the CBC and PCC). The following achievements were remarkable: management was placed in the hands of the churches, technical assistance from the DED in the area of pedagogy was taken over by the churches concerned and all the posts of pedagogic advisers hitherto held by the Germans were handed over to Cameroonians. In September 2008 the need to extend the programme to primary schools and decentralise seminars to school level was conceived and these went operational in phase four. From February to July 2010 a scientific evaluation was carried out by a team from the University of Edangen-Nuremburg Germany. The outcomes were fairly satisfactory and the recommendations were for the ISTP team as a whole to continue in the direction of the learner-centred concept, improve school quality and teacher professionalism, boost self-esteem of students by helping them cope with class heterogeneity and reduce training duration for Multipliers from two years to six months.

The main focus of phase five is to enforce monitoring and mentoring of teachers, continue with lesson observation and post-lesson discussions with teachers, conduction of demonstration lessons, facilitation of training workshops for students on peer education, health and HIV/AIDS issues and gender awareness, hold special training workshops for newly recruited teachers, set up pedagogic rooms in the various schools, and promote environmental education (including water monitoring and Wins Water Champion Award- Africa).

From inception till present, the programme has received support from the German Development Service (DED), Evangelischer Entwicklungsdienst.V (EZE), and German Protestant Development Service (EED) and more recently from Bread for the World - Protestant Development Service, Germany. (ISTP Journal of 24th April, 2010).

The objectives are achieved through the training of teacher trainers, on-the-job training of teachers, school visits, and conduction of workshops for teachers at subject levels, workshops for school administrators, school club coordinators and peer education for students. The teacher trainers trained by the ISTP are called Multipliers. After a full time training of between one to two years, they are posted to various schools where they carry out the multiplier activities of the ISTP concept. There is continuous pedagogic update of Multipliers to equip them with modern and quality trends in education. There is continuous monitoring by ISTP Pedagogic Advisers of the CBC and PCC education departments.

The duties of pedagogic ISTP Multipliers relating to instructional supervision include monitoring of teachers' attendance, regularity and effectiveness in the classroom, checking and marking of lesson notes/lesson plans, checking of schemes of work/diary of work, observing teachers' lessons, assessing the need of, planning for and facilitating pedagogic seminars/workshops at school levels, organising teachers to work in groups for the purpose of scientifically finding solutions to identified problems in the school, moderating examination questions and marking guides, providing guidance and assistance to new/inexperienced teachers and evaluation of instructional improvement.

Worthy of note is the fact that we are at the onset of the third millennium and it is a time when phenomena are generally evolving faster than ever before and the evolutions in these phenomena have a lot to bear on the educational system. This is drawn from the idea of Adeyemo (2000) where he holds that education and politics are symbiotic and that no educational system can escape from the political community in which it operates; the system must reflect what the political community wants it to do. The educational sector is the major sector which determines economic growth and hence development and political stability of a nation. To this end the school system is obliged to structure its principles such that learners are adequately prepared during their time of schooling to be eligible to compete in the local and global job market thereafter. These rapidly changing trends include changes in the demands of the government, changes in community expectations, constant fiscal crisis, decline in quality and quantity of teachers, changes in core values, changes in demand for education, technological changes, changes in the student population, changes in the family structure, changes in perceptions of efficacy among teachers

as a logical consequence of the above changes (The Sector Wide Approach on Education, 2005).

Out of these phenomena that of constant fiscal crisis seems to be the most influential; reason being that almost every sector of the economy besides intending to serve the citizens in their domain of expertise has as main aim profit maximisation. This implies that proprietors are bound to be more meticulous about the use of resources in their establishments be they human, financial or material. The schools are the establishments of interest in this study and the most practical way to ascertain that the personnel are using the resources rightly is by supervision and a performance appraisal. The ISTP Multipliers are part of the human resources in the Education Department of the CBC and a performance appraisal of their work is relevant in the said meticulous management of resources.

Furthermore, another prevailing factor in the context of this study is the professional status of a bulk of the teachers in the Education Department of the CBC; they mostly have academic degrees and this is being compensated by continuing professional assistance through the pedagogic ISTP team. Therefore to do a performance appraisal of the work of these internal supervisors from the teachers' perspective is as relevant as taking measures to manage the material, financial and human resources in the system properly.

From an economic perspective, a performance appraisal is likely to ensure better management of scarce resources as problems or weaknesses will be identified and addressed. From an academic perspective, the secondary education sub-system is plagued by many problems, some of which can be addressed by the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers. Research findings have shown that supervision of instruction in schools is inadequate; for example according to Titanji and Yuoh (2010) Regional Pedagogic Inspectors of English Language are not doing their job at acceptable levels and good interpersonal relationships do not exist between teachers and Regional Pedagogic Inspectors of English. Commenting on these findings they wrote "ineffective instructional supervision hurts teachers, students and schools as formal organisations. It deprives teachers of in-service development opportunities, especially within a context wherein many teachers have not received any professional training prior to assuming teaching responsibilities". All these situations point us to the significance of effective supervision of instruction in the school system.

The study is carried out in a context when "supervisors and teachers engage in dialogue for the purpose of improving instruction which logically should contribute to student improved learning and success" (Hoy & Forsyth, 1986; Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2002; Sullivan & Glanz, 1999;) cited in Baffour-Awuah, 2011. According to the same author, many researchers believe that supervision of instruction has the potential to improve classroom practices, and contribute to student success through the professional growth and improvement of teachers. Supervision is viewed as a co-operative venture in which the supervisor and the teacher engage in dialogue seeking solutions to problems that impede higher levels of teacher performance.

All of these buttresses the fact that supervision is one of the solutions to the problems plaguing the school. In the Sector

Wide Report on Education (2005), chapter four states as objective the amelioration of the efficiency and quality of education and the sub objective is to significantly reduce school dropout in secondary general education. The considerations for this in secondary general education according to this same report is to bring the completion rate from 27% in 2003 to 35% by 2015 in the first cycle and from 11% in 2003 to 13% by 2015 in the second cycle. This can be attained by ensuring the proper functioning of the internal supervisory system of instruction in the schools.

METHODOLOGY

This study used the case study research design. This design requires the collection of data using a questionnaire, interview guide or a combination of both instruments. For the purpose of this study data were collected using the questionnaire. This is a design which is geared towards a thorough understanding of a given unit under study. In the context of this study the unit under investigation was the internal supervisors of instruction in CBC secondary schools of the NWR of Cameroon, known as the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers.

In addition, a close ended questionnaire was used in order to collect data from many teachers about the performance of the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers who are charged with instructional supervisory responsibilities within the CBC education sub-system. This design was chosen for the study because the researcher intended to provide a thorough, in-depth and comprehensive and well-ordered information on teachers' performance appraisal of the said internal supervisors of instruction in the aforementioned unit.

The study area was found in the NWR of Cameroon. It covered five of the eight divisions of this region. The study was carried out specifically in the CBC secondary schools found in this region. The schools are six in number and are distributed as shown on table 3.

Table3: Distribution of schools in the study area by division and sub-division

Division	Sub-division	Name of school
Boyo	Belo	Baptist Comprehensive High School (BCHS) Njinikem.
Bui	Kumbo Central	Chaffee Memorial Baptist College (CMBC) Kumbo.
Donga Mantung	Ndu	Joseph Merrick Baptist College (JMBC) Ndu.
Mezam	Bamenda III	Baptist Comprehensive College (BCC) Nkwen.
Mezam	Bamenda II	Baptist High School (BHS) Mankon.
Ngoketunjia	Ndop Central	Baptist High School (BHS) Ndop.

This study used the proportionate and random sampling techniques. The reason was to ensure that teachers from all the schools were represented in equal proportions. There were a total of 179 teachers in all the schools and the sample was made up of 127 of these. The number of respondents from each school was obtained by multiplying the number of teachers in the school by two-thirds (2/3). This operation was performed and any answer with a decimal value of less

than 0.5 after the whole number was rounded off to the nearest whole number and where the decimal value was greater than 0.5 it was rounded up to the nearest whole number.

The data collected from the field were analysed aided by the use of statistical packages for social sciences (SPSS) version 21.0 for windows. Results were reported using descriptive statistics (such as frequencies, percentages and means).

Table 4: Distribution of sample by schools

Name of school	Number of teachers (minus Pedagogic ISTP Multipliers)	Number of teachers constituting the sample
BCHS Njinikijem	30	20
CMBC Kumbo	25	17
JMBC Ndu	38	26
BCC Nkwen	28	19
BHS Mankon	39	26
BHS Ndop	29	19
Total	179	127

The instrument used for data collection in the study was a Likert type questionnaire with structured items on the summated rating scale. The questionnaire was backed by a cover letter from the University of Buea authorising for research to be done in the schools concerned

The one-way student t- test was used to compare mean scores of respondents in the items pertaining to the research questions. For items in section B of the instrument (those which pertained to the research questions) their coded values were used to compute means. In doing this all „strongly agree' and „agree' responses were summed up and all the „disagree' and „strongly disagree' responses summed up. This is because these two broad groups of responses are positive and negative, respectively; the difference is only in the degree to which the responses in those groups differ. Their means were then computed as means favourable and unfavourable for each group of items relating to the research questions. These gave an avenue to compare means and the outcomes used as a basis on which to accept or reject the hypotheses of the study.

The mean scores which were statistically significantly lower than the expected mean led us to reject the alternative hypotheses and accept the null. Alternatively, where the mean scores were statistically significantly high the null hypotheses were rejected and the alternative hypotheses accepted.

FINDINGS

The findings of this paper are presented according to the main issue under investigation

Table 4: Appraisals of the usage of interpersonal skills

ISTP Multipliers' Attributes	% Responses			
	SA	A	D	SD
The relationship between the ISTP Multiplier(s) and the teachers is characterised by mutual respect for each other.	17.5	18.3	40.5	23.8
The ISTP Multiplier(s) in my school see(s) me as a good teacher and one who can do better in the teaching profession	16.7	29.4	31.0	23.0
The ISTP Multiplier(s) of my school use(s) the authoritarian approach in supervision of instruction	34.9	23.0	25.4	16.7
The ISTP Multiplier(s) of my school use(s) the democratic approach in supervision of instruction	8.0	21.6	33.6	36.8
The ISTP Multiplier(s) of my school use(s) the laissez-faire approach in supervision of instruction	12.0	18.4	42.4	27.2
The nature of communication between the ISTP Multiplier(s) and teachers is one-way	34.9	31.0	23.0	11.1
The nature of communication between the ISTP Multiplier(s) and teachers is reciprocal	4.0	23.4	35.5	37.1
The ISTP Multiplier(s)/Multipliers' language and context of communication to teachers is within reach.	9.6	33.6	24.8	32.0
The ISTP Multiplier(s) of my school is/are a good listener(s)	7.9	30.2	34.9	27.0
He/she/they listen(s) to teachers' complaints/difficulties	7.9	27.0	25.4	39.7
He/she/they suggest(s) timely solutions to teachers' complaints and difficulties	5.6	19.8	31.7	42.1
The ISTP Multiplier(s) pose(s) himself/herself/themselves as a „know all'	15.9	41.3	25.4	17.5
He/she/ they use(s) interpersonal skills	4.8	21.4	20.6	53.2

Figure 1: Bar chart representation of responses on use of interpersonal skills

Table 5: Distribution of responses on usage of interpersonal skills

Response	Frequency	Percentage
SA	6	4.8
A	27	21.4
D	26	20.6
SD	67	53.2
Total	126	100

Figure 2: Bar chart of responses on usage of interpersonal skills

The table reveals that out of 126 respondent’s majority strongly disagreed and disagreed to the fact that the Multiplicators make use of interpersonal skills; 93 respondents accounting for 73.8% as against 33 strongly disagreed and disagreed that the Multiplicators make use of interpersonal skills in supervision of instruction giving a percentage of 26.2%. This gives a negative picture on the whole; so, they do not use interpersonal skills at acceptable levels. This might either be because the Multiplicators did not develop these skills during training or their working conditions do not motivate them to use interpersonal skills at acceptable levels.

Effect of respondents’ gender on their view of use of interpersonal skills by pedagogic ISTP Multiplicators

Table 6: Effect of gender on pedagogic ISTP Multiplicators’ disposition to listen to teachers

GENDER	ISTP Multiplicators listen to teachers’ complaints/difficulties			SD	TOTAL
	SA	A	D		
Male	6(8.7%)	27(39.1%)	16(23.2%)	20(29.0%)	69(100%)
Female	3(6.50%)	6(13.0%)	9(19.6%)	28(60.9%)	46(100%)
Total	9(7.8%)	33(28.7%)	25(21.7%)	48(41.7%)	115(100%)

$\chi^2 = 13.601, df = 3, P = 0.004$

A significantly higher proportion of female respondents (60.0%) strongly believed that ISTP Multipliers do not listen to teachers' misfortunes while up to 39.1% of males believe they do listen ($\chi^2 = 13.601$, $df = 3$, $P = 0.004$). Both the female (52.2%) and male (31.9%) respondents agreed that the ISTP Multipliers pose themselves as „know all“ ($\chi^2 = 9.039$, $df = 3$, $P = 0.029$).

Table 7: Effect of gender on View of ISTP Multipliers' attitude towards teachers during observation

Gender	The ISTP Multiplier(s) pose(s) himself/herself/themselves as 'know all'				Total
	SA	A	D	S	
Male	10(14.5%)	22(31.9%)	20(29.0%)	17(24.6%)	69(100%)
Female	10(21.7%)	24(52.2%)	8(17.4%)	4(8.7%)	46(100%)
Total	20(17.4%)	46(40.0%)	28(24.3%)	21(18.3%)	115(100%)

$\chi^2 = 9.039$, $df = 3$, $P = 0.029$

Effect of respondents' current position on their view of approach used by pedagogic ISTP Multipliers

Table 8: Effect of position on view of the laissez faire attitudes of pedagogic ISTP Multipliers to teachers during observation

Position of respondent in school	The ISTP Multiplier(s) of my school use(s) the laissez-faire approach in supervision of instruction				Total
	SA	A	D	SD	
Principal	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(100%)	0(0.0%)	2(100%)
Vice Principal	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	3(100%)	0(0.0%)	3(100%)
Head of Department	8(23.5%)	7(20.6%)	7(20.6%)	12(35.3%)	34(100%)
Teachers	6(8.0%)	12(16.0%)	38(50.7%)	19(25.3%)	75(100%)
Others	0(0.0%)	3(50.0%)	1(16.7%)	2(33.3%)	6(100%)
Total	14(11.7%)	22(18.3%)	51(42.5%)	33(27.5%)	120(100%)

$\chi^2 = 22.942$, $df = 12$, $P = 0.028$

Concerning views on use of the laissez- faire approach the trend varied from negative to positive views with a drift down the hierarchical ladder ($\chi^2 = 22.942$, $df = 12$, $P = 0.028$). The same pattern was noticed in their views of use of interpersonal skills ($\chi^2 = 22.908$, $df = 12$, $P = 0.029$).

Table 9: Effect of position on view of use of interpersonal skills by ISTP Multipliers

Position of respondent in school	use of interpersonal skills by ISTP Multipliers				Total
	SA	A	D	SD	
Principal	1(50.0%)	1(50.0%)	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(100%)
Vice Principal	1(33.3%)	0(0.0%)	1(33.3%)	1(33.3%)	3(100%)
Head of Department	2(5.7%)	5(14.3%)	10(28.6%)	18(51.4%)	35(100%)
Teachers	2(2.7%)	17(22.7%)	13(17.3%)	43(57.3%)	75(100%)
Others	0(0.0%)	3(50.0%)	1(16.7%)	2(33.3%)	6(100%)
Total	7(68.0%)	26(21.5%)	25(20.7%)	64(52.9%)	121(100%)

$\chi^2 = 22.908$, $df = 12$, $P = 0.029$

Effect of respondents' duration of teaching experience on their view of use of interpersonal skills

Responses based on the number of years of professional experience of respondents significantly influenced two important attributes about the ISTP Multipliers. Respondents with less than 5 years (43.8%), between 5-10 years (40.7%) and between 15-20 years (48.3%) of experience strongly disagreed with the existence of any reciprocal communication between the ISTP Multipliers and teachers. Those between 10-15 years (60.7%) and > 20 years (37.5%) of experience disagreed with the claim ($\chi^2 = 25.498$, $df = 12$, $P = 0.013$).

On the other hand, despite the strong disagreement over the use of interpersonal skills by the ISTP Multipliers, the intensities of their responses were significantly variable ($\chi^2 = 21.590$, $df = 12$, $P = 0.042$).

Table 9: Effect of duration of professional experience on communication between pedagogic ISTP Multipliers and teachers

Duration of professional experience of respondent	The nature of communication between the ISTP Multiplier(s) and teachers is reciprocal				Total
	SA	A	D	SD	
< 5 years	0(0.0%)	8(50.0%)	1(6.3%)	7(43.8%)	16(100%)
5 - 10 years	1(3.7%)	7(25.9%)	8(29.6%)	11(40.7%)	27(100%)
10 - 15 years	0(0.0%)	3(10.7%)	17(60.7%)	8(28.6%)	28(100%)
15 - 20 years	1(3.4%)	5(17.2%)	9(31.0%)	14(48.3%)	29(100%)
> 20 years	3(12.5%)	6(25.0%)	9(37.5%)	6(25.0%)	24(100%)
Total	5(4.0%)	29(23.4%)	44(35.5%)	46(37.1%)	124(100%)

$\chi^2 = 25.498$, $df = 12$, $P = 0.013$

Discussion of findings for Hypothesis

The null hypothesis accepted states that the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers do not use interpersonal skills in supervision of instruction at acceptable levels. ISTP Multipliers are to make use of interpersonal skills if the supervisory process must go on smoothly and be productive enough to improve staff competence. This finding is consistent with the opinion of Callahan, Clark and Kellough, (1992) who hold that in exercising these interpersonal skills the supervisor has to provide adequately for individual differences of the teachers and to do this, "the supervisor must know something about the teacher's strengths, weaknesses, interests, goals, backgrounds and attitudes and such information may be obtained using tools like observation, conferences and questionnaires".

Interpersonal skills extend to the area of building relationships with protégés. This includes verbal and non-verbal communication with teachers. Petty (2004) holds that supervisors' expectations affect teachers' performance in the direction of that expectation. This implies if a supervisor thinks a teacher is good he gets better and on the contrary if the supervisor thinks the teacher is bad he gets worse. Petty adds that this self-fulfilling prophecy is operational in almost every conceivable teaching-learning situation from nursery teaching to the teaching of adult professionals. Hence, the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers have to key into their role with the mindset that their clients are good and can become better. Findings on this aspect of pedagogic ISTP Multipliers' view as to whether the teachers are good and can become better revealed the figures 54% who strongly disagreed and disagreed to the claim as against 46% who agreed and strongly agreed with the claim. A mindset of optimism about clients will consciously or unconsciously be revealed in the nature of interpersonal relations between the supervisor and the teacher thereby, encouraging the teacher to put in his or her best. With this in mind the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers would likely treat the teachers as such (that is, as people who are headed for success) thereby, increasing their chances of becoming better practitioners.

In addition, pedagogic ISTP Multipliers have to use the various forms of power with care because; according to Mbua (2003) if a boss applies these forms at random the results may be undesirable thereby, affecting the supervisory process negatively.

Another aspect of interpersonal skills which findings revealed that it is not used by the Multipliers includes; the right levels, models and dimensions of interpersonal communication. To be able do this Buber's, (1970) theory cited in Wood (1999) gives the way out. The I-Thou level + the transactional model=standard dimension of interpersonal communication which immerses the Multipliers in empathy; this is the threshold of the real professional help to the teacher, Westbrook *et al*, (2009). Prochaska & Diclemente, (1986) wrote "clients differ in what they bring to therapy and consideration of these factors by the Multipliers can ease the development of a good relationship". These facts have often been neglected; that is why 65.9% of responses on one-way nature of communication were affirmative as against 34.1%, 72.6% of the responses denied that the Multipliers' communication is reciprocal as opposed to 27.4% who's views on this was affirmative.

A significant advantage of the I-Thou level of communication is advanced by Stewart (1986) when he writes "only in I-thou relationships do we become fully human and there we discard the guises we use most of the time and allow ourselves to be completely genuine in interaction." Wood's (1999) transactional model of interpersonal communication is ideal for adoption by the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers because according to this model, interpersonal communication is continuously a changing process and not static so that the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers should "label" teachers and penalise them consciously or unconsciously for a "prejudice" they may have harboured against the client for some time. The other strength of this model is that it does not label one person "sender" and the other receiver. Instead they are both termed communicators participating equally and often simultaneously in the process. Aegyle and Dean (1965) cited in Weitz (1974) also suggest that eye contact and distance balance each other out so that approach and avoidance tendencies are equalised at the level of eye contact and distance chosen as "comfortable" by "interactants".

Movement and gestures should equally be managed with care because they though being non-verbal are capable of passing messages across to the client whether when the "communicator" was intentional about it or not. Dittmann (1972) cited in Weitz (1976) opines that body movements occur at times of "nonfluency" in verbal interaction and may possibly accompany the speech encoding process within the individual. To Schefflen (1972) cited in Weitz body language acts as control mechanism monitoring the interaction and the "interactants" within it. Every comment a person makes and every action in which he engages can be subject to attributional analysis by self and by others. Other ways of building a positive supervisor-teacher relationship include the following: listening, advising; deflecting probing and reflecting.

Gaining power and influence is an aspect of interpersonal skills which from findings the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers are below standard as more than half of the respondents hold that the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers adopt the authoritarian style (57.9%) in supervision of instruction while only 29.6% attest to their use of democratic style. To Whetten & Cameron (2011) supervisors must display a balanced view of power watching against overuse (abuse) of the power wielded to them by virtue of their position in the organization; this when it happens can breed resistance from the teacher which is an outright inhibitor to the success of supervision and professional growth. They must equally watch against an underuse of the said power because it would breed *laissez-faire* as manifested in absenteeism, use of class time for irrelevant discussions, absence of lesson planning and lateness on the part of the teachers. This power should be properly used in managing interpersonal conflicts. This begins with diagnosing the focus and source and choosing the right strategy to solve it (Whetten & Cameron, 2011).

Being a good listener is one of the interpersonal skills which from findings is only made use of very timidly. Prove of this is the aggregate positive and negative scores on the item "The ISTP Multiplier(s) of my school is/are a good listener(s). Only 38.1% of the responses were positive as against 61.9% for negative responses on this item. As to whether they listen to teachers' difficulties and complaints we had only 34.9% of

respondents with positive responses on this; meaning that up to 65.1% of them attest that the Multipliers do not listen to them. This is contrary to the plea of Petty (2004) when she advances that a listening ear soothes the client and facilitates the two (therapist and client) to find the appropriate solution to the issue at hand.

Recommendations of the Study

Based on the findings and conclusions arrived at the following recommendations were made to the various categories of people who are prospective beneficiaries of the findings of this study:

The Education Secretary of the CBC

The education secretary of the CBC should visa for a change in the way the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers function in the system. They should have a road map/calendar of activities prepared to show quantitative evidence as to the number of teachers with whom they are currently working at a given period and a chart duly prepared by the pedagogic ISTP Multiplier and his/her protégé to show areas of professional development achieved within a given period. This period could range from one month to one term depending on the nature of the predicament that was earlier on identified and worked upon. In this way the Multipliers will be given every provision to display their expertise at full range without any reason for haste. This also rolls out any possibility of wanting to use the same supervisory approaches for all teachers irrespective of their individual needs and longevity in the profession.

The ISTP Coordinator

It was also recommended that the ISTP Multiplier should consider increasing the duration of training for the Multipliers seeing that findings revealed the possession but mediocre use of knowledge and further investigations revealed same mediocrity in usage of the skills that should validate their possession of the expertise. The extended training duration should be dedicated to internships in order to give them ample opportunity to match theory with practice before they graduate.

It was also recommended to the ISTP coordinator that an award be designated and given from his office to the best performing Multiplier annually. This will serve as a form of motivation to the Multipliers to do their job well.

The Principals of CBC secondary schools in the NWR

It was also recommended that a support dialogue between the principal (of the school concerned) and the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers be introduced and done on as regular basis as once every month. This is a school-level discussion between the principal and each of the pedagogic ISTP Multipliers one-on-one. It is a conversation about performance needs in order to address the needs. The use of a Performance Improvement Plan for each pedagogic ISTP Multiplier was also recommended. This plan has a formal structure and can be used for notifying a pedagogic ISTP Multiplier of “unacceptable” performance. Both tools may be used for all pedagogic ISTP Multipliers, regardless of the entry level and duration of the “therapy” for them. The tools may also be used independently of each other. Table 10 shows the differences between the two processes.

Table 10: Tools to increase efficiency of pedagogic ISTP Multipliers

	Support dialogue	Performance improvement plan
Purpose	For Multipliers who are in need of additional support. These Multipliers attempt to fulfil the Standards but are often ineffective.	For Multipliers whose work is unsatisfactory
Initiates process	Principal or Multiplier	Principal
Documentation	Form provided: none. Memo or other record of the discussion/other forms of documentation at the school level.	Form required: performance improvement plan. School level/ISTP coordinator is notified.
Outcomes	Performance improves to proficient discontinue support Some progress- continue support. No progress the Multiplier may be redeployed to the training centre.	Sufficient improvement- recommendation to continue status as Multiplier. Inadequate improvement- recommendation to either cease being a Multiplier or redeploy to training centre.

Source: Adapted from Mecklenburg county public schools Teacher Performance Evaluation (TPE) System (2012/2013) Handbook.

The ISTP Multipliers

It was recommended that the Multipliers should put themselves to task responding to the appraisal of their clients. This can be achieved if their point of departure is a desire to help the teachers become better practitioners than they were before their interaction. This has the benefit of helping them trace the way forward in their functions as „helpers“ of teachers. This may be facilitated by the analogy of the Multiplier-teacher relationship to that of the physician- his patient. The physician’s first joy is to see the patient cured before the remunerative part which follows thereafter.

The teachers of the CBC secondary schools in the NWR

It was recommended that these teachers be more eager and more available to the Multipliers. In this way, they might help the Multipliers to help them better given that they make the first move towards their supervisors, inviting them to observe their lessons, owning up to specific challenges and letting the Multipliers attend to them. In this way, the Multipliers would be moved to the point of being more intentional about individual teachers’ needs.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abell, S. K. (2007). *Research on science teacher knowledge: Handbook of research on science education*. Mahwah, NJ/London: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Publishers.
- [2] Acheson, K. A., & Gall, M. D. (1980). *Techniques in the clinical supervision of teachers*. New York: Longman.
- [3] Acheson, O., Keith A., Gall, K., Meredith D. (1977). *Techniques in the clinical supervision of teachers: Pre-service and in-service applications*. USA: Longman Publishers.
- [4] Akinwumiju, J.A. & Agabi, C.O. (2008). *Foundations of School Management*. Port Harcourt: University of Port Harcourt Press.
- [5] Amin, M. E., (2005). *Social science research: Conception, methodology and analysis*. Makerere University press: Kampala.
- [6] Archibong, F.I. (2008). *Quota Admission System and Quality Output in the Federal Government Colleges in Rivers State*. Unpublished M.Ed. Thesis, University of Port Harcourt.
- [7] Ary, D., Jacobs, L. C., & Razavieh, A. (1996). *Introduction to research in education* (5thed). Orlando, FL: Harcourt Brace & Company.
- [8] Baffour-Awuah, P. (2011). Supervision of instruction in public primary schools in Ghana: Teachers' and head teachers' perspectives. University of Cape Coast Ghana.
- [9] Baxter, L. A. & Braithwaite, D. O. (2008). *Engaging theories in interpersonal communication: Multiple perspectives*. Sage Publications Ltd: London- UK.
- [10] Beach, D. M., & Reinhartz, J. (1989). *Supervision: Focus on instruction*. New York: Harper & Row.
- [11] Beach, D. M., & Reinhartz, J. (2000). *Instructional leadership*. Needham Heights, MA: Allyn & Bacon.
- [12] Beauchamp, T. L., & Bowie, N. E. (1997). *Ethical theory and business*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [13] Becker, G.S. (1994). *Human Capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis with special reference to education*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- [14] Blasé, J. & Blasé, J., (1998). *Handbook of instructional leadership*, Thousand Oaks: CA Corwin Press.
- [15] Bransford, J., Brown, A., & Cocking, R. (Eds.). (2001). *How people learn: Brain, mind, experience, and school*. Washington, DC: National Research Council.
- [16] Bryk, A.; Schneider, B. (2002). *Trust in Schools: A Core Resource for Improvement*. New York: Russell Sage Foundation.
- [17] Bubb, S. (2005). *Helping teachers develop*. Paul Chapman Publishing: London.
- [18] Callahan, J.F., Clark, L.H., & Kellough, R.D., (1992). *Teaching in the middle and secondary schools* (4thed). Macmillan Publishing Company: New York.
- [19] Campbell, J.M. (2000). *Becoming an Effective Supervisor*. Philadelphia: Accelerated Development.
- [20] Carey, N., & Frechtling, J. (1997). *Best practices in action: Follow-up survey on teacher enhancement programs*. Arlington, VA: National Science Foundation.
- [21] Carroll, M. (1996). *Counselling Supervision: Theory, Skills and Practice*. London: Cassell.
- [22] Cawelti, G. (1999). *Handbook of research on improving student achievement* (2nd ed.). Arlington, VA: Educational Research Service.
- [23] Chassot, A.I.; Schroeder, E.O.; Del Pino, J.C.; Salgado, T.D.M. & Krüger, V. (1993). Química docotidiano: pressupostos teóricos para a elaboração de material didático alternativo. Espaços da Escola (Ijuí – RS), 3 (10), 47-53.
- [24] Chuo, M. J. (2007). *Teacher performance appraisal of regional pedagogic inspectors in the North-West and South West regions of Cameroon*. Unpublished Master's Thesis- University of Buea.
- [25] Clark, A.O. (2000). *Elements of Business Communication*. Mindex Publishers: Nigeria.
- [26] Cogan, M. L. (1973). *Clinical supervision*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- [27] Cook, A. & Mack, M. (1971). *The head teacher's role*. New York: Citation Press.
- [28] Daining, C. (2005). *Resilience of youth in transition from out-of-home care to adulthood*, Unpublished dissertation, University of Maryland: Baltimore
- [29] Dewey, J. (1938). *Experience and education: The latter works of John Dewey*. Southern Illinois University press.
- [30] Edited by Bligh, D. (1982). *Accountability or freedom for teachers?* Direct Design Ltd. Guildford. (Norman Lindop), Neil merit, Brain Gowenlock & David Warrenpiper, Mary Warnock)
- [31] Edited by Flint C, (1987) *Changing Education*, Stanley Thornes Publishers Ltd, Leckampton, England.
- [32] Elliot, J. (1991). *Action research for educational change*. Philadelphia: Open University Press.
- [33] Epah, F. G. & Vukeh, T.E. (2009). *Secondary school administration and principalship* (2nded). Presses Universitaires d "Afrique.
- [34] Feldman, A. (2005). *Enhancing the practice of physics teachers: Mechanisms for the generation and sharing of knowledge and understanding in collaborative action research*. Research report, University of Massachusetts: Amherst, U.S.
- [35] Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. New York, Seabury.
- [36] Fullan, M. (2003). *Planning and coping with change: Strategic leadership and educational Improvement*. Thousand Oaks CA, Sage Publications.
- [37] Gick M. L., & Holyoak K. J. (1987). "The cognitive basis of knowledge transfer": *Contemporary research and applications*. New York: Academic Press.
- [38] Ginsburg, H., & Opper, S. (1979). *Piaget's theory of intellectual development* (2nded). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [39] Glatthorn, A. A. (1997). *Differentiated supervision* (2nded). Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.

- [40] Glickman, C. D., (1990). *Supervision of instruction a developmental approach*. Boston; Allyn & Bacon.
- [41] Glickman, C. D., Gordon, S. P., & Ross-Gordon, J. M. (1995). *Supervision of instruction* (3rded). Needham Heights, MA: Simon & Schuster.
- [42] Glickman, C. D., Gordon, S. P., Ross-Gordon, J. M. (1998). *Supervision of instruction: A developmental approach* (4thed). Boston: Allyn & Bacon.
- [43] Glickman, C. D., Gordon, S. P., & Ross-Gordon, J. M. (2001). *Supervision and instructional leadership* (5thed). Needham Heights, MA: Allyn & Bacon.
- [44] Goldhammer, R., Anderson, H., Krajewski, R. & Robert, J. (1993). *Clinical supervision: Special methods for the supervision of teachers* (3rd Ed.). Stout: Rinehart and Winston Inc.
- [45] Goldhammer, R., Anderson, R. H., & Krajewski, R. J. (1993). *Clinical supervision: Special methods for the supervision of teachers* (3rded.). New York: Holt, Rinehart, & Winston.
- [46] Guskey, G. (2002). *Evaluating professional development*. Thousand Oaks, CA, Corwin Press.
- [47] Halim, L. (2009). *Research on pedagogical content knowledge on science and mathematics education in Malaysia*. Bangi: Fakulti Pendidikan, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.
- [48] Hammond, M. & Collins, R. (1994), *Self- directed learning: Critical practice*. Kogan Page Ltd: Pentonville Road, London.
- [49] Harwood, R., Miller, S. A., & Vasta, R. (2008). *Child psychology: Development in a changing society*. Hoboken: NJ John Wiley & Sons.
- [50] Haynes, R. (2003). *Clinical supervision in the helping professions: A practical guide*. Pacific Grove: Brooks/Cole.
- [51] Heimlich, J. E. & Norland, E. (1994). *Developing teaching style in adult education*. Jossey Bass Inc. Publishers, San Francisco: California.
- [52] Hersey, P., Blanchard, K. H., & Johnson, D. E. (2001). *Management of organizational behaviour: Leading human resources* (8thed). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice- Hall.
- [53] Holloway, E.L. (1997). *Structures for the analysis and teaching of supervision*. In C.E. Watkins.(Ed.), *Handbook of Psychotherapy Supervision* (pp. 249-276). New York: Wiley.
- [54] Hunt, J. (2009). *US politician quoted by Linda Darling-Hammond, 2009*. Hoboken: NJ John Wiley & Sons.
- [55] Johnson, L. & Bauer, A. M (1992). *Meeting the needs of special students: Legal, ethical, and practical ramifications*. Newbury Park, GA: Gorwin Press.
- [56] Joyce, B. & Showers, B. (2002). *Student achievement through staff development*. New York: Longman, Inc.
- [57] Katz, L. G. & Weir, M. K. (1969). *Help for preschool teachers: A proposal urbana*. IL ERICC learning, House on Early Childhood Education, ED031308.
- [58] Killer, G.(1998). *Jackson Public School District Teacher Performance Evaluation Handbook*,
- [59] Kitchener, K. S., Lynch, C. L., Fischer, K. W., & Woord, P. K. (1993). *Developmental range of reflection judgment: The effect of contextual support and practice on developmental stage*. *Developmental Psychology*, 29 (5), 893-906.
- [60] Levine, S. I. (1989). *Promoting adult growth in schools. The promise of professional development*. Needham heights, Mass: Allyn Bacon.
- [61] Lortie, D. C. (1975). *School teacher: A sociological study*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- [62] Maarof, N. (1974). *Non- verbal communication: Readings with commentary*. New York Oxford University press: London.
- [63] Marks, H. M., Newmann, F. M., and Gamoran, A. (1996). *Does authentic pedagogy increase student achievement?* In F. M. Newmann & Associates (Eds.), *Authentic achievement: Restructuring schools for intellectual quality*, SanFrancisco: Jossey- Bass.
- [64] Mbua, F. N., (2003). *Educational administration: Theory and practice*. Limbe: Design House.
- [65] Mitchell, R. (1995). *The communicative approach to language teaching, an Introduction: In Teaching Modern Languages*. Ann Swarbrick (ed.). London: The Open University.
- [66] McAdams, D. (2006). *The person: A new introduction to personality psychology* (4thed) Mish, F. C. (Ed.). (1989). *The new Merriam-Webster dictionary*. Springfield, MA: Merriam-Webster.
- [67] Moir, M. (2014). *New teacher centre*. University of California, Santa Cruz: Winsconson Education Association Council.
- [68] Montgomery, D. (1999). *Positive teacher appraisal through classroom observation*. London: David Fulton.
- [69] Moswela, B. (2010). *Instructional supervision in Botswana secondary schools: An Investigation on educational management and leadership*. Unpublished M. Ed Thesis.
- [70] Muchinsky, P. M. (2006). *Psychology applied to work (8th ed)*. Belmont, CA: Thomson Wadsworth.
- [71] Muchinsky, P. M. (2012). *Psychology Applied to Work (10th ed.)*. Summerfield, NC: Hypergraphic Press.
- [72] Myers, D. G. (2007). *Psychology: 8th Ed in modules*. Worth publishers: 41 Madison avenue New York.
- [73] Neugarten, B. (1989). *Life span development and research on aging*. New York, Aldine.
- [74] Nwagwu, N.A., Ijeoma, M.E. & Nwagwu, C.C. (Eds.). (2004). *Organization and Administration of Education: Perspectives and Practices*. Benin City: Festa Printing Press Ltd.
- [75] Nworgu, B. C. (1991). *Educational research: Issues and methodology*. Lagos, Nigeria, Wisdom Publishers Ltd.
- [76] Okafor, P. (2005- 2010). *Leadership in instructional supervision*. Edited by Foxit Corporation, 2005-2010, for evaluation only.

- [77] Ovens, A. (2004). *Telling his or her story through reflective journals*. The Association for Office
- [78] Petty, G. (2004). *Teaching today: A practical guide (3rded)*. Nelson Thornes Ltd: Delta Place, UK.
- [79] Piaget, J. (1968). *Six psychological studies*. Random House: New York.
- [80] Pierce, R.A. & Rowell, J.S. (2005). *The 10 Keys to Effective Supervision: A Developmental Approach*. Rising Sun Consultants.
- [81] Ralph, E. G. (1998). *Developing practitioners: A handbook of contextual supervision*. Stillwater, OK: New Forums Press
- [82] Reiman, A. J., & Thies-Sprinthall, L. (1998). *Mentoring and supervision for teacher development*. New York: Addison Wesley.
- [83] Rettig, P. R., Lampe, S & Garcia, P. (2000). "Supervising Your Faculty with a Differentiated Model." Reprinted with permission from Anker Publishing, Inc.
- [84] Robins, A. & Callan, S. (2009). *Managing early years' settings*. SAGE Publications Ltd: London.
- [85] Ross, P. H., Ellipse, M.W. & Freeman, H.E. (2004). *Evaluation: A systematic approach* (7th ed.). Thousand Oaks: Russell Sage Foundation.
- [86] Schiro M. S. (2008). *Curriculum theory: Conflicting visions and enduring concerns*. Sage Publications, 2455 Teller Road, California.
- [87] Schultz & Schultz, Duane (2010). *Psychology and work today*. New York: Prentice Hall.
- [88] Serdyukov, Peter, and Ryan, Mark. *Writing Effective Lesson Plans: The 5-Star Approach*. Boston: Allyn & Bacon, 2008.
- [89] Sergiovanni, Thomas J. (1991). *The principalship: A reflective practice perspective* (2nd Ed.). Boston: Allyn and Bacon.
- [90] Sergiovanni, T. J., & Starratt, R. J. (2002). *Supervision: A redefinition* (7th ed.). New York McGraw Hill.
- [91] Sheal, P. (1985). *Classroom observations: Training the observers*. Longman.
- [92] Stufflebeam & Brethower. (1987). *The new handbook of teacher evaluation: Assessing elementary and secondary school teachers*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications.
- [93] Stufflebeam, D. L., & J. R. Sanders. (1990). *Using the Personnel Evaluation Standards to improve teacher evaluation*. In J. Millman & L. Darling- Hammond (Eds.),
- [94] Sullivan, C. G. (1980). *Clinical supervision: A state of the art review*. Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development (ASCD).
- [95] Tambo, L.I. (2003). *Cameroon national education policy since the 1995 forum*. Limbe: Design House.
- [96] Tambo, L.I. (2012). *Principles and methods of teaching* (2nd ed.). Limbe: Design House.
- [97] *The Handbook of the Association of American Schools in South America* (AASSA). The Mecklenburg County public schools teacher performance evaluation system (TPES) (2012-2013).
- [98] The Republic of Cameroon (2005). *Report on the sector wide approach to education*. SOPECAM, Yaounde.
- [99] Vaillant, G. E. (1977). *Adaptation to life*. Cambridge, MA. Harvard University Press
- [100] Veenendall, T. L., DeVito, J. A. & Smith, C. B. (1992). *The interpersonal communication handbook* (6thed). Harper Collins College publishers: New York.
- [101] Wallace, P.M. & Goldstein, J.H. (1994). *An introduction to psychology* (3rded). WM. C Brown communications Inc.
- [102] Warmbrod, J. R. (1986, March). *Priorities for continuing progress in research in agricultural education*. Paper presented at the 35th Annual Southern Region Research Conference in Agricultural Education, North Little Rock, AK.
- [103] Webb, L. D., Metha, A., Jordan, K. F. (1991). *Foundations of American education*. New York, Macmillan Publishing Company.
- [104] Westerbrook, D., Kennerly, H., & Kirk, J. (2009). *An introduction to cognitive behaviour therapy: Skills and applications*. SAGE Publications Ltd: Oliver's Yard, London.
- [105] Whetten, D.A, Cameron K.S. (2011). *Developing management skills* (8thed). Prentice Hall: New York
- [106] Williams, M. (1991). *In- service education and training*. Villier's House: London.
- [107] Wlodkowski, R. J. (1985). *Enhancing adult motivation to learn*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- [108] Wolfe, S. (2006). *Your Best Year Yet! A Guide to Purposeful Planning and Effective Classroom Organization (Teaching Strategies)*. New York: Teaching Strategies.
- [109] Wood, J. T. (1999). *Interpersonal communication everyday encounters* (2nd ed.). Wardsworth Publishing Company: USA.
- [110] Wood, L.C., Nicholson, W. E. & Findley, G. D. (1985). *The secondary school principal: Manager and supervisor* (2nded). 7 Wells Avenue: Newton, Massachusetts.

ARTICLES

- [1] Broady-Preston, J. & Steel, L. (2002). *Employees, customers, and internal marketing strategies in LIS. Library Management, 23, 384-393.*
- [2] Cederblom, D. (1982). *The performance appraisal interview: A review, implications, and suggestions*. Academy of Management Review, 7(2), 219-227.
- [3] Cummings, L. L. & Schwab, D. P. (1978). *Designing appraisal systems for information yield*. California Management Review, 20, 18-25.
- [4] Darling-Hammond, L., & McLaughlin, M. W. (1995). *Policies that support professional development in an era of reform*. Phi Delta Kappan, 76(8), 597- 604.
- [5] DeNisi, A. (2000). *Performance appraisal and performance management: A multilevel analysis*.
- [6] DeNisi, A. & Pritchard, R. (2006, July). *Performance appraisal, performance management, and improving individual performance: A motivational framework*. Management and Organization Review, 2(2), 253-277.

- [7] Jordan, P., Phillips, M. & Brown, E. (2004). *We train trenchers: Why not supervisors and mentors?* Physical Educator: Winter, 61 (4): 219-221.
- [8] Rahman, S., Mohdjas, Z., & Osman, K. (1999). *The conception, perception and the practice of reflective thinking among student teachers.* (Report No. G6/99). Bangi: Fakulti Pendidikan, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.
- [9] Showers, B. & Joyce, B. (1996). *The evolution of peer coaching: Educational leadership.* 53(2), 12-16.
- [10] Simkovic, M. (2013). "Risk-based student loans": *Washington and Lee Law Review* 70 (1): 527. SSRN 1941070.
- [11] Smith, M. K. (1996). *The functions of supervision: The encyclopaedia of informal education.*
- [12] Todd D (2007). *GEF Evaluation Office Ethical Guidelines.* Washington, DC, United States: Global Environment Facility Evaluation
- [13] Tucker, P. D. & Stronge, J. H. (2005). *Linking teacher evaluation and student achievement.* Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- [14] Zon, K. (1994). *Philosophy of ethics and teaching practice in teacher education.* In Rashidi Azizandan Abdullah Mohd. Noor (Eds.), *Teacher Education: Challenges, philosophy and strategies in developing effective teachers,* Faculty of Education, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.
- [9] Glatthorn, A. A. (1997). *Differentiated supervision* (2nd ed.). Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- [10] Hummel, H., Manderveld, J., Tattersall, C. and Koper, R. (2004) "Educational modelling language and learning design: new opportunities for instructional reusability and personalised learning", *Int. J. Learning Technology*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp.111-126.
- [11] Hunter, M. (1988). *Create rather than await your fate in teacher evaluation.* Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- [12] *International Education Journal*, Vol. 8 (1) (2007), pp. 205-220.
- [13] *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)* e-ISSN: 2320-7388, p-ISSN: 2320-737X Volume 1, Issue 3 (Mar. -Apr. 2013), PP 13-19 www.iosrjournals.org
- [14] ISTP; *Vision twenty fifteen: The learner at the centre.* Journal of 1st September, 2012.
- [15] *ISTP's goals, sectors of action, organisational structures, historical development, achievements and impacts and challenges.* 1st September, 2014.
- [16] *Journal of counselling & development* *March/ April 1993* Volume 71.
- [17] *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 16 (3) (1990), pp. 235-254.
- [18] *Journal of Physical Education New Zealand*, 37 (1) (2004), pp. 45-60

JOURNALS

- [1] Abu-Doleh, J. & Weir, D. (2007). *Dimensions of performance appraisal systems in Jordanian private and public organizations.* *International journal of human resource management*, 18(1), 75-84.
- [2] *Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development (ASCD)*, 1250 N. Pitt Street, Alexandria, VA 22314-1453; fax: 703-299-8631 (member price, \$13.95; non-member, \$16.95).
- [3] *Basic Research Journal of Education Research and Review* ISSN 2315-6872 Vol. 2(1) pp. 06-15
- [4] Cook, G. E. (1996). *Using clinical supervision to promote inquiry.* *Journal of Staff Development*, 17(4), 46-50.
- [5] Darling-Hammond, L., & McLaughlin, M. W. (2009). *Policies that support professional development in an era of reform.* *Phi Delta Kappan*, 76, 597-604.
- [6] Edmeirer, H., & Nicklaus, J. (1999). *The impact of peer and principal collaborative supervision on teacher's trust, commitment, desire for collaboration, and efficiency.* *Journal of Curriculum and Supervision*, 14(4), 351-378.
- [7] *Fairfax County Public Schools Department of Human Resources.* TPE program handbook (2012-2013). January 2013 Available online <http://www.basicresearchjournals.org> Copyright ©2013 Basic Research Journal.
- [8] Gagne, R. M., & Wiegand, V. K., (1968). *Some factors in children's learning and retention of concrete rules.* *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 59(5), 355- 361.
- [19] *Journal of Research & Method in Education.* Volume 1, Issue 3 (Mar. -Apr. 2013), PP 13-19, www.iosrjournals.org
- [20] Kanfer, R. & Ackerman, P. L. (1989). *Motivation and cognitive abilities: An integrative/aptitude-treatment interaction approach to skill acquisition.* *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 74, 657-690.
- [21] Maddocks, J. & Beaney, M. (2002). *See the invisible and intangible.* *Knowledge Management.* March, 16-17.
- [22] Manasa, K. & Reddy, N. (2009). *Role of training in improving performance: The IUP journal of soft skills*, 3, 72-80.
- [23] Muczyk, J. P. & Gable, M. (1987, May). *Managing sales performance through a comprehensive performance appraisal system.* *Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management*, 7, 41-52.
- [24] Njobati, F. F. (19th December, 2013). *Overview of ISTP phases down memory lane.*
- [25] Pettijohn, L., Parker, R., Pettijohn, C., & Kent, J. (2001). *Performance appraisals: usage, criteria, and observations.* *The Journal of Management Development*, 20, 754-771.
- [26] Prideaux, D. *BMJ* (2003); 326 doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmj.326.7383.268> (Published 01 February 2003).
- [27] *Report on Evaluation of ISTP; PCC & CBC secondary schools.* (April, 2004). CBC Printing Press, Bamenda.

- [28] Richard, C. G. (2002). *The performance appraisal question and answer book: Survival guide for managers.* 28-29.
- [29] Robert, A.L (1976). "Collective bargaining and in-service education" *ph Delta Kapan* pp 468 – 469.
- [30] Ronnestad, M.H. & Skovholt, T.M. (1992). *The evolving professional self: Stages and themes in therapist and counsellor development.* Chichester, England, Wiley.
- [31] Ronnestad, M.H. & Skovholt, T.M. (1993). *Supervision of beginning and graduate students of counselling and psychotherapy.* Journal of career development.
- [32] Schraeder, M. Becton, J., & Portis, R. (2007, Spring). *A critical examination of performance appraisals.* The Journal for Quality and Participation, 20-25.
- [33] Selden, S. C., Ingraham, P. W., & Jacobson, W. (2001). *Human resource practices in state government: Findings from a national survey.* Public Administration Review, 61(5), 598-607.
- [34] Smith, A.: *An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations* Book 2 – Of the Nature, Accumulation, and Employment of Stock; Published 1776.
- [35] Spinks, N., Wells, B., & Meche, M. (1999). *Appraising appraisals: computerized performance appraisal systems.* Career Development International, 4(2),94-100.
- [36] Sudarsan, A. (2009). *Performance appraisal systems: A survey of organizational views.* The Icfai University Journal of Organizational Behaviour, 3(1), 54-69.
- [37] *The ISTP pedagogic concept and "the new challenge".* 24th April, 2010.
- [38] Twomey, D. & Harris, D. (2000). *From strategy to corporate outcomes: Aligning human resource management systems with entrepreneurial intent.* International Journal of Commerce and Management, 10, 43-55.
- [39] Wanzare, Z., & Da Costa, J. L. (2000). *Supervision and staff development: Overview of the literature.* NASSP Bulletin, 84(618), 47-54.
- [5] Elisa, M.O. (2011). "Creating social change: One career at a time", retrieved from <http://www.elisamortiz.org>.
- [6] Elizabeth, A.D (1974). "Staff development: whose job is it? Educational leadership ,pp 137 140.
- [7] Fink, D. L. (2005). *Integrated course design.* Manhattan, KS: The IDEA Center. Retrieved from http://www.theideacenter.org/sites/default/files/Idea_Paper_42.pdf
- [8] Guiney, E. (2001). *Coaching isn't just for athletes: The role of teacher leaders.* Phi Delta Kappan, 82(10). Retrieved May, 10, 2002, from Fullan, M. (2011). *Learning is the Work.* May 2011. Trent Ray © 2013 Expanding Learning Horizons. All rights reserved. 1300 653 164 www.expandinglearninghorizons.co
- [9] Holland, P. E. (2004). *Principals as supervisors: A balancing act.* NASSP Bulletin, 88 (3), 1-14. doi: 10.1177/019263650408863902
- [10] Hurteau, M., Houle, S., Mongiat, S. (2009). "How Legitimate and Justified are Judgments in Program Evaluation?" *Evaluation* 15 (3): 307-319. doi:10.1177/1356389009105883.
- [11] Kearsley, G. (2003). *Andragogy (M Knowles).* Retrieved January 16, 2004. Available from <http://tip.psychology.org/knowles.html>.
- [12] Koper, R. (2000). *From change to renewal Educational technology foundations of electronic learning Environments.* Retrieved from DSpace OUNL site <http://hdl.handle.net/1820/38>
- [13] O'Bannon, B. (2008). "What is a Lesson Plan?". Innovative Technology Center * The University of Tennessee. Retrieved May 17, 2011.
- [14] Palloff, R. & Pratt, K. (2002). *Didactic material production: Learning to teach.* <http://gemini.ricesu.com.br/colabora/n10/index1.htm>
- [15] Reeve, J. & Paperboy, D. (2007). "Evaluating the evaluation: Understanding the utility and limitations of evaluation as a tool for organizational learning". *Health Education Journal* 66 (2): 120-131. doi:10.1177/0017896907076750.
- [16] Reischman, J., (2000). *Andragogy, homepage for adult education specialists.* Retrieved, February 26 2004 from <http://www.uni-bamberg.de/ppp/andragogik/andragogy/>.
- [17] Robin, W. (2012). *Why are associate professors some of the unhappiest people in academe? The chronicle of higher education,* <http://chronicle.com/article/why-are-associate-professors/132071/>
- [18] Staff, . (2011). "Evaluation Purpose": *Lessons in effective teaching.* Learning Technologies at Virginia Tech. Retrieved 13 May 2012.
- [19] Timperley, H. (2007). *Teacher Professional Learning and Development: Best Evidence Synthesis Iteration [BES].* Wellington, New Zealand: Ministry of Education. Available at www.educationcounts.govt.nz/goto/BES
- [20] Wanzare, Z., & Da Costa, J. L. (2000). *Supervision and staff development: Overview of the literature.* NASSP Bulletin, 84(618), 47-54.

INTERNET SOURCES

- [1] Atherton, J. (2003). *Knowles' andragogy.* Retrieved February 18, 2004 from <http://www.dmu.ac.uk/~jamesa/learning/lnowlesa.htm>
- [2] Brennen, A. M. (2008). *Clinical supervision and case study. Articles and resources on educational administration and supervision.* Retrieved from <http://www.soencouragement.org/clinical-supervision-case-study.htm>.
- [3] Darling-Hammond, L. (1996). *What matters most: A competent teacher for every child.* Phi Delta Kappan, 78(3). Retrieved January 5, 2004, from <http://www.pdkintl.org/kappan/darling.htm>
- [4] Douglas, L.I. (2009), *Modern leadership styles in the changing world.* Eastern University, ChangingMinds.Org.